

DUAL-T Interview topic guide

Participant Group	Main theme	Example questions/probes
Professional literary translators	Preferred workflow(s)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Discuss workflow preferences as emerging from the post-task questionnaire (Q1). <p><i>“Overall, you indicated Workflow # as your preferred workflow and Workflow # as your least favourite.</i></p> <p><i>For each workflow, could you elaborate on the specific features you found particularly useful?</i></p> <p><i>Could you now elaborate on the particular features you did not find particularly useful?”</i></p>
	Effort/Temporal perceptions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Temporal effort (Q2) <p><i>“You selected Workflow # as the fastest workflow and Workflow # as the slowest. Could you elaborate on the reasons behind your choice for each of the workflows?”</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Technical/Cognitive effort (Q3) <p><i>“You selected Workflow # as the one requiring more effort and Workflow # as the one requiring less effort. Could you specify which elements of each workflow led you to this choice?”</i></p>
	Segmentation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Discuss post-task questionnaire answers on segmentation preference. (Q4) <p><i>“You selected Workflow # as having the best segmentation and Workflow # as having the worst one. Could you describe in more detail the reasons why a line-by-line segmentation or a full-page view is preferable for you?”</i></p>
	Impact on overall process	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <i>Overall, would you say your translation process changed in any way according to the workflow you were using?</i>
	Would you implement any of the tools you have used	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> You answered 'Yes/No' to this question (Q5).

	<p>today in your current workflow?</p>	<p>Yes:</p> <p><i>“You said in the questionnaire that you would adopt Workflow # in the future. How would Workflow # augment your current workflow?”</i></p> <p>No:</p> <p><i>“You said in the questionnaire that you would not adopt any of the workflows used today. What aspects of your current workflow do you prefer as opposed to the workflows you worked with today?”</i></p>
	<p>Previous use of translation technology (CAT and PE)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Discuss pre-task questionnaire answers on previous use of CAT tools and PE (Q10 & Q11 of pre-task questionnaire) <p>(Q10) <i>“You previously mentioned (not) using Computer-Aided Translation (CAT) tools in your literary translation activity.</i></p> <p>Yes: <i>How often would you say you translate literary texts using CAT tools?</i></p> <p><i>What are the main reasons for using CAT tools?</i></p> <p>No: <i>What would you say are the main reasons for you not having used CAT tools for literary translations?”</i></p> <p>(Q11) <i>“You also mentioned (not) using postediting for literary translation.</i></p> <p>Yes: <i>How often would you say you translate literary texts using postediting?</i></p> <p><i>What are the main reasons for using postediting?</i></p> <p>No: <i>What would you say are the main reasons for not having used postediting for literary translation so far?”</i></p>

	<p>Workflow features in the future + change of perceptions + conclusion</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Discuss features participants would like to see in future workflows. <p><i>“Are there any specific features/apps/tools you would like to see developed and/or adopted in the future of literary translation? If so, which ones? If not, why?”</i></p> <p><i>“Overall, has participating in this study changed your perceptions of translation technology tools? In what way?”</i></p>
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